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Materials and construction systems

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND PROPOSAL FOR SUSTAINABLE ACOUSTIC PANELS BASED ON PLANT FIBRES FROM INVASIVE SPECIES AND RECYCLED MATERIALS. APPLICATION TO THE CASE OF *PENNISETUM SETACEUM*

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Abstract

The climate emergency demands sustainable constructions for the care of our planet, calling for the substitution of conventional materials that are harmful to the environment [Figure 1] with new natural materials that respect the ecosystem [1]. The design of acoustic panels with vegetable fiber combined with recovered and recycled materials allows us to explore the development of a versatile and experimental ecological methodology [2]. The applicability of these materials would be related to fields such as architecture, music, engineering, education, health, etc., requiring controlled acoustic conditions, being a transversal and multidisciplinary project [3 y 4].

Figure 1: *examples of acoustic conditioning based on materials harmful to the ecosystem.*

This project proposes the creation of acoustically effective materials based on materials and/or plant waste from invasive plants that affect ecosystems, allowing them to be controlled and reducing their environmental impact [5], mixed in different proportions with other residual and recycled materials [6]. The methodology consists of a process of creating prototypes of panels with different densities, fibre sizes and mixtures of materials for subsequent analysis of their acoustic characteristics (Figure 2) [7]. The results presented here are the tests carried out with the *Pennisetum setaceum*, known as cat's tail (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Process, development and treatment of the acoustic and ecological material

For the measurement of the sound absorption coefficient, the UNE-EN 12354-6 standard [8] was followed using an impedance tube - Kundt's tube - (Figure 3) equipped with a loudspeaker and two microphones (Figures 4 y 5) [9 y 10], inferential statistics tools and materials for the absorption of acoustic energy and other possible uses in closed enclosures according to the ASTM C384-98 standard [11].

Figure 3: Kundt tube from the laboratory of the "Sonic Chrystal Technologies" research group of the UPV, Gandía.

These vegetables allow the development of acoustic materials that constitute, on the one hand, an alternative to the classic materials used in construction (Figure 6) [12] and, on the other hand, offer an ecological solution to the problems related to invasive plants and environmental care.

Figure 4: Traditional acoustic materials: rock wool, polyurethane foam and honeycomb foam.

Tests carried out with various cellulosic materials and their combinations (Figure 5) desvelan, reveal, in some cases, an effective characteristics of acoustic absorption, improving the response of traditional materials (Figure 6) [13 y 14], ideal for the field of acoustic conditioning in construction [15].

Figure 5: prototype samples with different ecological plant materials

Figure 6: Fibreglass sound absorption curve (5cm.)

The most effective materials for acoustic absorption will be cat's tail, common reed and palm tree and their combinations, providing optimal results in their acoustic conditions [16], allowing to obtain a significant absorption coefficient at medium and high frequencies, depending on the cellulose material used, improving with whole and long fibres (Figure 7), the density of the material, preferably low, its porosity and its specific thickness.

Figure 7: samples with plant materials and combined with stone materials.

The results of the *pennisetum setaceum* tests have been compared with conventional fibreglass panels, highlighting the good characteristics of the samples, with the M31 sample reaching an acoustic absorption value close to 0.9 as a result of the absorption coefficient at frequencies between 800 and 2000 Hz, and 0.8 between 2000 and 3150 Hz (Figure 8) [12]. These samples, with low density and high porosity, show satisfactory results despite being 3cm thick, while conventional materials are 5cm thick. [17].

Figure 8: Curves of *Pennisetum setaceum*

Given the polyvalence and versatility of these composites, as well as the good results obtained with little mass and thickness, the next steps of this research project are the development of self-supporting acoustic panels that can be used in projects and deployable constructions [18] for the conditioning of fixed, changing, transformable and ephemeral closed spaces for both architectural and artistic installations [19].

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